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Analysis of the Public Space in the Old Sana'a City

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ABSTRACT

The formation of public spaces contributes to improving the quality of urban life to achieve comfort and health for urban communities. public spaces are an important component of any urban formation because they contain the various activities of the inhabitants. They are among the elements that reflect the overall image of the city and the relationship between humans and the environment in which they live. This study aims to describe the significance of public spaces as places for social interaction and cultural activities and their benefits from several social, economic, and environmental aspects in the old Sana'a city as a case study. This study relied on analytical and descriptive methodologies to reach the research objective. This study concluded the balanced distribution between public spaces and buildings in the city, and the diversity of their functions to suit the needs of the city's residents. It also contributed to raising the economic and social level and improving the climate among the residential neighborhoods by providing shades and reducing the temperature through narrow, curved streets.

Keywords

Public Space, Old Sana'a City, Activities, Benefits, Functions, Elements.

1. Introduction

There are many previous studies on public spaces in cities in general, where it was mentioned that open spaces are one of the most important components of the structure of the built environment, which is everything that surrounds buildings, such as corridors, squares, open spaces, green spaces, water bodies, playgrounds, private and public gardens, and parking lots and roads. And this is what we find in the formation of the ancient Yemeni cities, especially the historical city of Sana'a, where we find that it is one of the most successful means of maintaining the balance of the environment, as it is considered one of the basics of urban planning that is working to establish it.

Some previous local studies referred to the public places of the old city of Sana'a but in a simplified and not detailed way that shows the importance of public space in reviving the city and the extent of its impact on

its residents from several social, economic, and environmental aspects. Old Sana'a is a lively and historical city. It is a mixture of public places that have heritage values. These public spaces can be described as relics of past events, professions, and possessions. And in the context of the historic living city, the community activities inherited hundreds of years ago are the source of vitality.

In this study, the old city of Sana'a, which was included in the World Heritage List, was selected as a case study, which is the political capital of the Republic of Yemen. It is the most important cultural center in Yemen and was previously selected as the capital of culture in the Arab world in 2004. The ancient Yemeni architects relied on the formation and construction of the old city of Sana'a on functional environmental foundations and principles and specific techniques that considered the environment amazingly and sustainably. The old city of Sana'a still contains many environmental, social, and economic features due to the formation and design of the public space until the present time.

2. The benefits of public spaces:

In this paper, various benefits are shown, including social, economic, and environmental, which are as follows:

2.1. Significance of public space in revitalization the historic living city:

Public spaces are an essential feature of a city's livability because they encourage daily activities as well as special events such as religious festivities, marriages, and other social gatherings. At the same time, they reflect social networking and face-to-face connection, economic revitalization, and effects on the local climate. It also emphasizes the value of public space in creating a feeling of place and community by supporting local activities and different events that are part of the city's culture, thus revitalizing the city. In the historical city, public spaces that facilitate daily and social activities are an important source of life.

2.2. Social and psychological benefits:

Public spaces play a vital role in the social development of people at different levels and are places of great value as they allow people from various cultures and ethnicities to meet and showcase their culture and at the same time experience new cultures unfamiliar to them. Integration and social interaction can be achieved through:

- 1) Providing picnic areas and places to sit and meet.
- 2) Providing places for children to play with swings and slides and others that help children play in a safe place.
- 3) Providing sports facilities such as football, basketball, tennis, and other fields.
- 4) Providing a sense of safety: avoiding dangers and accidents (separating motorized movement from pedestrians, avoiding closed places, providing lighting).

This is what has been considered in the formation of the public space of the historic city, but it always needs restoration and increased provision of seats and attention to landscaping around green spaces or squares where people can gather.

2.3. Environmental benefits:

1) The open spaces in old Sana'a were characterized by their narrow alleys that make the buildings close together, sometimes touching their roofs, and even roofing in some parts. It helps to reduce the area exposed to the sun, i.e., create shadows as much as possible, reducing the heat gained.

2) The proportion between the areas of green spaces and the area of buildings in the old city, and this ratio corresponds to the creation of appropriate local climatic conditions, as it is commensurate with the daily life of the residents and their social activities.

3) Narrow streets between buildings help in improving the climate and achieving the proportions of air movement and the required shades.

4) Reducing pollution through green spaces, which spread in most residential neighborhoods in the old city and are surrounded by buildings on all sides. In the past, they used it to grow vegetables and what the neighborhood needed, and it was called the skimmer. However, these areas were neglected by afforestation due to the war and the absence of the government.

2.4. Economic benefits:

A good public landscape offers very clear benefits to the local economy in terms of:

1) Stimulating rising housing prices, as homebuyers are willing to pay near green spaces.

2) Positive impact on real estate prices where proximity to public places adds economic value and creates tax revenue.

3) Achieving economic demand for housing units overlooking urban areas.

4) Connecting spaces with movement paths related to economic activities in the region.

5) Tourism increases the economy's revenue, produces thousands of jobs, and helps a nation's economy improve. Tourism creates many jobs in a variety of fields. Tourism to these public places increases financial flows.

3. Analysis of public space in the old city:

Urban spaces are classified in residential communities according to several considerations, including what is related to their gradations and function in cities (main - sub...) and some are classified according to the specificity of that space (public or private) and this is related to the number of users and their social groups, and some of them are related to the type of movement, where the space is usually affected by the purpose for which it was created.

The following is an analysis of the formation of the public space of old Sana'a into three important parts figure (1), which are the features of streets, green spaces, and markets:

3.1. Street layout shape:

The road network in the old city of Sana'a comes in a variety of forms, ranging from wide to narrow, narrow to curved, because of planning according to demand and environmental factors. Figure (1)

Generally, the road network of the city can be divided into the following categories:

1) Main road: internal public space connecting the community with the city center, as well as the main traffic axis and gate to the main external road.

2) Secondary streets: represented by semi-public spaces that connect the lane centers on one side, and to the city center on the other.

3) Sub-streets (Narrow alleys): These are spaces reserved for the residents of the neighborhood. They branch off from secondary roads and are connected at their ends with other alleys, or they are closed at the end and overlook on both sides of the entrances to the houses.

Figurer 1: (a) The map of planning the streets in Old Sana'a city; (b) Survey area in old city.

Source: (a) (Naeem, 2015); (b) (Farwan T. H. & et al., 2009)

3.2. The formation of green space:

Green spaces in Old Sana'a constitute one-fifth (1/5) of the total area of the Old City. Each community has its own large green space. It is noted that the presence of green spaces is one of the most important features of the planning of the old city of Sana'a to integrate green nature with the urban environment. In the old city of Sanaa, there is an orchard in each neighborhood. The number of orchards in the area is about 40. It is noted that the presence of green areas is one of the most important features of the planning of Sana'a. According to many historical documents, the inhabitants of the vicinity of the old City of Sana'a used to grow vegetables through these orchards as the food they needed. Figure (2).

Figurer 2: Map to show the green spaces.

Source: <https://www.qahtaan.com/vb/showpost.php?p=599536&postcount=1>.

3.3. The formation of markets (suq):

Suq is the name of the market or the street which contain markets. One of the most important features of the Islamic market system is function classification. It is related to their status of the mosque. The old market is indicated to the Great Mosque of Sana'a, there are a network of markets, commercial centers and street. The market is in a middle place in the heart of the old city of Sana'a, east of Al-Saila (name of rain road), between Bab Al-Yemen (name of gate) in the south and (name of gate) in the north, the length of Old Sana'a, which does not exceed 2 km, between these two gates, there are (1911) small shops according to the census of the competent authorities. It consists of several markets, each dedicated to an important craft or merchandise. The old Sanaa market is one of its main distinguishing features, which is a civilized and material product for successive ages considering it one of the markets of the pre-Islamic Arabs. (Soltanzadeh H., Moghaddam M. S., 2015)

It consists of several markets, each of which focuses on an important craft or commodity. The old Sana'a market is one of its main features. Considering that it is one of the markets of the pre-Islamic Arabs, it is a civilization and material product of the past. Because the city has participated in the caravan trade, its commercial influence has gained international influence. The ports of the Red Sea and the Indian Ocean connecting to the north of the Arabian Peninsula have continued to this day. The area of the market may be small at first and then expanded to include the buildings attached to it, the broker (khans). The area of the current market is 48,000 m², of which 27,000 m² are built, while the area of brokers is 6,400 m². The number of Sana'a markets has reached about thirty markets. Figure (3).

Figure 3: A map showing the extension of the historical market.

Source: (Naeem, 2015)

4. The function and characteristic of public space element:

These spaces took a place where they had their functions that met the requirements of social needs and environmental requirements, and all of them had their meanings and identity, which were consistent with various environments and related to human behavior and ways of life and its link to many jobs, whether in the center, markets, groups, or mosques, as well as the job that was related to environmental aspects climatic and social. And its shape is greatly affected by the type and importance of its components and the type of activity. Accordingly, the spaces can be divided into:

- **Static void:** It is a wide space that suggests calm and stability. It is a place for gathering and emphasizes social relations between users. It is represented in public and main squares and residential areas.
- **Dynamic space:** It takes a linear shape and suggests movement as it pulls the eye to a specific target, and it is represented in commercial corridors, roads, streets, and extended spaces such as the corniche and entertainment corridors.

This research will clarify the functional characteristics of the elements of public space as follows:

4.1. Types of Streets:

4.1.1. Narrow streets:

The streets are narrow, allowing a single passage of movement by motorized vehicles because it was designed to cater only light volume of traffic especially animal-driven carriages. Street were public spaces where they were not only connectors to various other localities within the heritage zone but acted as intermediate spaces that connect the front of a neighbor's house to the other. In such a situation child played on the street, old folks would sit by the front of their houses chatting with neighbors.

However, in the current context, the large volume of traffic passing through these streets causes great discomfort and vibration to residents, threatening the stability of the building. Figure (4).

Figure 4: Type of narrow street in residential neighborhoods.

Source: <https://www.pinterest.com/pin/2533343529605065/>

4.1.2. Main Streets:

Broad Streets are wide, allowing large vehicles to pass in two or one directions, and There are sidewalks for people to pass. Because it leads to markets or service places or closes to the city entrance, traffic and noise are heavy. Figure (5).

Figure 5: Type of main street in residential neighborhoods.

Source : https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/2/20/Sanaa_%282884497718%29.jpg

4.1.3. Streets of the market stores (suq):

The streets of market is known as Suq. Suq is a place for the supply of the goods.

The old Sana'a Market has the following characteristics:

- 1) Market streets are generally narrow and not straight, according to the layout of urban streets.
- 2) A shop building with no more than one storey height and no residential space, as seen in a simple and primitive shop.

3) The market area is divided into sub-markets. Each branch specializes in a type of selling specific goods and specific craftsmanship. Distributed around the market are buildings that supplement market activities. These buildings are brokers and are dedicated to the establishment of merchants and their animal and

commodity shops. Figure (6).

Figure 6: Types of streets in market stores.

Source: (a) (Soltanzadeh H., Moghaddam M. S., 2015); (b) <https://www.iexplore.com/articles/travel-guides/middle-east/yemen/shopping-and-leisure>; (c) <https://www.alayyam.info/news/76882YHI-O2RDME>

4.2. Pedestrian paths:

4.2.1. linear space:

Linear space refers to the space extending around the protected area along with the fluid interface. This space is a key element connecting people and Al-Saila (name of rain road), and another important feature of the historic city of Old Sana'a. They also include those spaces behind the shops or urban houses in the back lanes behind the buildings. Figure (7).

Figure 7: (a) The face of linear space in old city. (b) A view of linear space round the Al-Saila interface.

Source: (a) Drawing by author; (b) <https://gulfnews.com/photos/news/photos-yemens-capital-sanaa-hit-by-flash-flooding-1.1586941866757?slide=16>

4.2.2. Pedestrian path behind the residential buildings:

The pedestrian corridor behind the residential units is considered a quiet and safe place away from the congestion of the corridors in front of the buildings linked to the public street. This gives privacy to these residential units, which are linked to the green spaces behind the buildings and are at the same level as the buildings, unlike the green spaces that are low. This makes the passers-by of people contemplate nature and its beauty at an elevated level. Although these spaces can be viewed as simply interconnected corridors at the back of the buildings, they also serve as meeting places for individuals and communities around a particular

area. Figure (8).

Figure 8: (a) *The Face of pedestrian path in old city*; (b, c) *A view of pedestrian path around green space*.
 Source: (a) *Drawing by author*. (b) https://www.aleqt.com/2016/04/15/article_1047359.html; (c) <https://horia.yoo7.com/t9-topic>

4.2.3. Pedestrian bridge for crossing the rain road:

The rain road is known as Al-Saila, which is divided between the old city before extended and the city after extended. The width of the road rain (Al-Saila) is about 30 meters, and the two parts of the city were connected by bridges above it, to facilitate the passage of people - especially when this road is filled with rainwater. This road was made to protect the old city of flood. Figure (9)

Figure 9: *The face of pedestrian bridge for crossing the Al-Saila*; (b) *A view of pedestrian bridge in old city*.
 Source: (a) *Drawing by author*; (b) <https://www.arabnews.com/node/1662731/middle-east>

4.3. Open spaces:

4.3.1. Squares:

Squares are wide places which are in front of the entrance to the old city or historic landmarks such as mosques, museums and others. Many people and tourists pass through these squares to enter and leave the city or visit some historic landmarks. In squares, there are parking lots for buses and cars, and entertainment

performances. Example the square near the south gate, it is characterized by its spaciousness, and it is next to the Al-Radwan Mosque (known as the Bab Al-Yemen Mosque due to its proximity to the old city gate). Figure (10)

Figure 10: (a) A view from up to show square in the entrance of old city; (b) A view from inside to show the square in the entrance of old city.

Source : (a) <https://eyooon.net/view.aspx?id=24903>; (b) <https://www.dreamstime.com/editorial-image-market-sanaa-yemen-old-town-image47787830>

4.3.2. Green space:

Residential buildings are surrounded by public green spaces. The public garden provides a semi-private spot for people to walk around, rest in, and feel comfortable in. It provides privacy for neighborhood residents as well as the opportunity for social interaction with their neighbors. In addition, these orchards, pavilions, and gardens are fields for growing all kinds of vegetables that the residents of each neighborhood need. These urban spaces in the city perform important environmental and economic functions, as they have been found to act as natural filters to purify the air from dust and dirt. It also helps raise the humidity and create shadows. Figure (11).

Figure 11: A view to show green space.

Source : <https://holmakhdar.org/resources/studies/1962/>

4.3.3. Wall and gates:

The old Sana'a has seven gates, some of which are old, and some have been used and have vanished, and only the Gate of Yemen remains. The old Sana'a has a huge wall with a length of (5-9) meters, dating back to the ancient Shebaan era. The city wall was built at the end of the second century AD. Given the thickness and immunity of the old wall, the surface of the wall can accommodate eight horses. Use the same lanes to pass the old cannon carts to defend the city to protect it from aggression. In Addition, this wall has 128 towers. Figure (12).

Figure 12: A view to show the wall and gate of Bab Al-Yemen in old city.

Source : <https://republicanyemen.net/archives/21736>

5. Conclusion:

This research analyzes the function of public space in the planning of the historic city of Sana'a, which is listed as one of the world heritage cities by UNESCO. Through that study, the following was found:

The relative balance in the distribution of land between residential buildings and public spaces, especially green spaces, constitutes one-fifth of the city's planning.

The public space of historical cities has multi-dimensional characteristics and serves different purposes. For this reason, different aspects were taken into consideration in the presented analysis, including the economic, social, and environmental benefits and the analysis of the functional features of the public space.

6. Recommendation:

The study recommends the following:

1. The function of urban gardens, which are unique elements of Sana'a's old city, must be preserved and its maintenance, especially because of the current political situation in the country and government neglect, which led to the exploitation of these public spaces, such as green spaces, to expand construction, and this will lead to the obliteration of this unique heritage of the old city.
2. Social squares must be preserved. These squares symbolize the daily social interactions that occur within the walls of Sana'a.

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